

Effects of flooding on insect pests and spiders in a rainfed rice environment

J.A. Litsinger, A.L. Alviola III, and B.L. Canapi, Entomology Department, IRRI

We studied a 1,000-ha tract of rainfed rice along the Cagayan River in northeastern Luzon, Philippines, planted to photoperiod-sensitive, traditional, Wagwag varieties. Farmers do not use fertilizers or pesticides. A kerosene light trap monitored daily

changes in insect populations; FARMCOP suction samples were taken from 20 hills in each of 4 experimental, double-cropped modern variety fields twice a week. Moisture status (soil surface dry or wet or depth of flooding) of 20 fields and rainfall were recorded daily.

Rainfall necessary for land preparation was erratic, causing transplanting of the single crop to span Jun-Dec. Most planting was done in Nov, after two typhoons in late Oct and early Nov. Flooding from those

typhoons averaged 0.5 m for several weeks.

At the onset of flooding, *Solenopsis geminata* ants prevalent in rice bunds formed melon-sized balls of workers protecting their reproductives, and these floated away with the floodwaters. Spiders spun masses of webs on shrubs along embankments at the edge of the floodwaters.

Field collections of hoppers and spiders were low after flooding (see figure). Migratory brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and whitebacked

Insect pest and spider predator numbers measured by FARMCOP suction machine in experimental direct-seeded (DSR) and transplanted (TPR) double rice crops compared to light trap catches reflecting the traditional single crop. Two typhoons caused flooding from the last week of October through the first 2 wk in Nov. Solana, Cagayan, Philippines, 1980-81.

planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* recolonized the area after the floods and numbers exploded with the minimal natural enemy pressure. The high numbers collected in the light trap 2 mo after the floods represented 2 generations of hopper buildup. Hopperburn occurred in 30 ha of traditional rice. Spiders recolonized too late to prevent planthopper resurgence. The less migratory green leafhopper

Nephotettix spp. were slow to recolonize. Also decimated by the floods, their numbers did not resurge after flooding.

Yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* represented 99% of the stem borers (SB) from dissected stems in this flood-prone environment. YSB larvae can survive in rice tillers underwater; larvae of other SB species perish. Maximum numbers of YSB

collected in the light trap near harvest probably represent an emigrant dispersal flight in response to crop senescence and dry fields. YSB does not aestivate during the dry season but recolonizes from tracts of irrigated rice 10 km away. Low numbers of YSB were collected in the light trap throughout the year. ♀

Effect of ratoon rice crop on populations of green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*, brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*, whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera*, and their predators

C. G. dela Cruz and J.A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

A 50- to 60-d-old ratoon rice crop following a 120-d-old transplanted crop extends the effective period of insect pest buildup from 3 to 5 generations. Because insect numbers increase exponentially with each generation, hoppers which are not restricted to specific crop stages might be favored by

a ratoon crop. A ratoon crop also may create a favorable environment for hopper predators after harvest of the main crop because it does not involve habitat-disturbing land preparation.

Two successive field trials were conducted at IRRI to study populations of major hopper species and their predators in the main crop, ratoon crop, and second transplanted crop.

Mature plants of IR1917 (insect-susceptible but rice tungro virus-resistant) were ratooned by cutting stalks 15 cm above the ground. No insecticide was used on any crop, but fertilization, irrigation, and weeding were done as recommended. Hoppers and their predators were sampled

intensively using a FARMCOP suction machine.

As the main crop matured, hopper populations declined naturally because of outward migration and natural enemy activity (see figure). Space-web and hunting spiders were most abundant in the first crop and were more prevalent than orb-web spiders.

On the subsequent ratoon, all spider groups were generally higher than on the second crop. Possibly, the spiders foraged from the ratooned plots to the second transplanted crop, explaining why hopper numbers in general were low in all second crops.

Hunting spiders, dominated by *Lycosa pseudoannulata*, maintained